

Artificial Islands, Installations and Structures as Protection Against Hybrid Attacks

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Abstract—This article will analyse the possibility under international law of building artificial islands, installations, and structures in the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) to protect critical maritime infrastructure against hybrid threats in accordance with the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). It will demonstrate that such entities may be used for protective purposes in the strictly limited framework of what is allowed by accessory competences derived from the critical infrastructures' economic use or an equity-guided balancing of interests. To the contrary, the establishment of large-scale maritime security architectures via the construction of these infrastructures remains unlawful.

Keywords—*Law of the Sea, UNCLOS, Exclusive Economic Zone, EEZ, Maritime Infrastructure, Hybrid Attacks, Artificial Islands, Safety Zones*

I. INTRODUCTION

The integrity of global maritime infrastructures is a fundamental prerequisite of the modern world economy. Over 99 % of intercontinental data traffic is transmitted through submarine cables, while energy security depends heavily on subsea pipelines and offshore wind farms [1]. The attacks on the Nord Stream pipelines in 2022, as well as incidents involving the Balticconnector, have exposed the great vulnerability of such maritime critical infrastructures [2]. Sabotage operations of this kind are increasingly carried out as hybrid attacks: Unlike conventional military sabotage, such attacks deliberately operate within a grey zone of international law, below the threshold of open armed conflict. Attribution to specific perpetrators is systematically impeded and deliberately concealed, for instance by instrumentalising civilian actors such as research vessels or the so-called shadow fleet [3].

Faced with this asymmetric threat landscape, the question of preventive protective measures is more pressing than ever for coastal States. One conceivable measure introduced in this paper is the physical safeguarding of infrastructures through the construction of artificial islands, installations or structures dedicated to the protection of sovereign interests. Such platforms could in turn host stationary surveillance systems, sensor networks, or physical barriers. While the laying of submarine cables and pipelines is subject to its own regime under the law of the sea (Article 79 UNCLOS), it may equally benefit from the protection of such installations. The central legal question of this paper is therefore: To what extent is the construction of artificial islands, installations and structures in the EEZ allowed by UNCLOS if their primary purpose is the protection against hybrid attacks?

II. ARTIFICIAL ISLANDS, INSTALLATIONS AND STRUCTURES

Article 60 UNCLOS establishes the coastal State's 'exclusive right to construct and to authorize and regulate the construction, operation and use' of artificial islands, installations and structures in its EEZ. The provision distinguishes between artificial islands on the one hand and installations and structures on the other, yet refrains from providing a legal definition of either term [4]. Drawing on the

definition of a natural island under Article 121(1) UNCLOS, an artificial island is understood as a permanent and human-made elevation above the sea level which rests on the seabed. In contrast to natural islands, however, an artificial island generates neither a territorial sea nor an EEZ or continental shelf of its own, pursuant to Article 60(8) UNCLOS. Its legal status is consequently not equivalent to that of sovereign territory [5].

Installations and structures, by contrast, encompass a broad spectrum of artificial constructions connected to the seabed that do not necessarily possess the characteristic of an island (e.g. drilling platforms, offshore wind energy installations, or permanently anchored sonar and surveillance stations) [6].

III. LAWFULNESS OF PROTECTIVE STRUCTURES IN THE EEZ

Assessing the lawfulness under international law of structures erected purely for protective purposes requires a precise balancing of the rights of the coastal State against the freedoms of the international community. Through its regulatory regime for the EEZ, UNCLOS establishes a carefully calibrated equilibrium that counterbalances the excessive pursuit of national security interests with the freedom of usage guaranteed to all other States.

A. *The Purposive Limitation of Article 60 UNCLOS*

The starting point is Article 60(1) UNCLOS, which provides that the coastal State has the exclusive right to authorise and regulate the construction of artificial islands (a); installations and structures for the purposes provided for in Article 56 and other economic purposes (b); and installations and structures which may interfere with the exercise of the rights of the coastal State (c).

An initial interpretive obstacle emerges with regard to installations and structures: Their construction is expressly tied to the 'purposes provided for in Article 56' (primarily the exploration and exploitation of natural resources) or to 'other economic purposes' [7]. The erection of stationary facilities whose sole purpose would be law enforcement or military threat prevention (such as large-scale underwater sensor networks) cannot readily be subsumed under that limitation of competences to economic purposes [8].

In order to justify such protective installations or structures, the following lines of argumentation merit consideration: Either the protective function is construed as an integrated operational safeguard of an installation ('security by design' as a component of subparagraph b), or it is treated as an ancillary competence for the effective exercise of the rights enshrined in Article 56 (*effet utile*). According to this last interpretation, infrastructure protection would not constitute an exclusive purpose for the construction of said infrastructure, but rather a necessary ancillary competence derived from the right to resource exploitation and which guarantees that such right be exercised effectively.

B. *The Distinctive Status of Artificial Islands*

Turning to the provision on artificial islands (Article 60(1)(a) UNCLOS), a notable asymmetry becomes apparent: Unlike subparagraphs (b) and (c) of Article 60(1), the provision on artificial islands contains no express purpose-bound limitation. The wording thus creates the appearance of a broad-reaching competence of the coastal State to build artificial islands in its EEZ and to regulate their construction, operation and use without any purpose-related constraint [9]. It was established earlier that the *effet utile* doctrine could guarantee the protection of critical maritime infrastructures by safeguarding the freedom to operate them *via* the construction of installations dedicated to their security. As artificial islands are not bound to a specific purpose, relying on the *effet utile* doctrine to guarantee the effective exercise of a right is not necessary.

From a historical perspective, however, there is ground to suggest that this differentiation should not be read as an affirmative decision in favour of unrestricted island construction for military purposes. It should rather be understood as a reflection of the enduring tension during the Third United Nations Conference on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS III) between far-reaching coastal State aspirations and the interests of major maritime powers, proponent of navigational freedoms [10].

More recent scholarship emphasises that the military use of the EEZ is not expressly regulated in the Convention, and that controversial positions and divergent State practice persist in this regard [11]. Against this background, the preferable view is to interpret Article 60(1)(a) UNCLOS as a broadly formulated, yet not unconditional, coastal State competence [12].

It follows that there is no incentive to deliberately conceive and construct protective infrastructures in the form of ‘artificial islands’ merely to avoid the purpose-bound limitation of subparagraph (b). While artificial islands are not subject to the same restrictions as installations and structures under that provision, their construction and use is by no means unconstrained: They remain subject to the coastal State’s due regard obligations under paragraph 3, to the requirement of conformity with international regulations under paragraph 5, and to the general framework of Part V [13]. The regulatory margin gained by choosing the legal form of an artificial island is therefore negligible.

C. *Principles Opposing Expanding Competences of the Coastal State in Matters of Protection*

Regardless of whether a facility is classified as an island or an installation, any expansion of coastal State competences for protective purposes goes against fundamental principles of the law of the sea. The EEZ, for instance, cannot form part of the sovereign territory of the coastal State [14]. The coastal State does not enjoy comprehensive territorial sovereignty there, but merely functional, sovereign rights tied to economic interests (Article 56 UNCLOS). Against this backdrop, the law of the sea scholarship has long warned of creeping jurisdiction, i.e. the gradual extension of functional coastal State competences at the expense of the freedoms of other States, which is generally regarded as unlawful [15]. This risk is addressed by Article 58(1) UNCLOS, which ensures that in the EEZ, in particular, freedom of navigation and overflight, as well as other internationally lawful uses of the sea associated with these freedoms, are preserved [16].

This does not mean that the coastal State cannot take any measure related to infrastructures; the Convention explicitly permits the establishment of artificial islands, installations and structures, as well as limited safety zones. However, a maritime infrastructure established for protective purposes stands on questionable legal grounds if the protective mechanisms it carries out go beyond the protected infrastructure’s necessary functions and disproportionately impairs the navigational freedoms of other States or disrupts recognised sea lanes essential for international shipping [17].

Finally, a reading of Article 58(2) in conjunction with Article 88 UNCLOS hints toward the fact that the EEZ, too, is reserved for peaceful purposes. However, no absolute prohibition of military infrastructures can be derived therefrom. Rather, scholarship and State practice demonstrate that the scope and meaning of this reservation remain contested, particularly with respect to military uses of the EEZ. Consequently, the establishment in the EEZ of infrastructures dedicated to military defence would provoke significant legitimation and interpretive conflicts, to be assessed against Articles 56 *et seq.*, 88 and 300 *et seq.* UNCLOS [18].

D. *The Systematics of Article 60 UNCLOS*

Additional arguments against maritime infrastructures dedicated to physical protection can be drawn from the systematics of Article 60 UNCLOS. In particular, paragraphs (2) through (7) tightly frame the competences of the coastal State and defines the substantive limits of their lawfulness. In principle, Article 60(2) UNCLOS grants the coastal State exclusive jurisdiction over maritime infrastructures, which also encompasses security aspects. This gives the right to the coastal State, for instance, to install physical and electronic defence measures directly on and around the installation.

For protection against threats emanating from the surrounding maritime space, Article 60(4) and (5) UNCLOS provide a specific mechanism: the establishment of safety zones. The systematic rationale resides in the fact that the Convention addresses the protection of maritime infrastructures conceptually through immaterial buffer zones rather than through the construction of autonomous physical defence structures in the surrounding area. Such safety zones may be proclaimed by the coastal State around its infrastructures and exist as accessories to those infrastructures. Physical defence mechanisms, by contrast, would possess a different character that is not envisaged in the relevant norms [19].

Can it therefore be concluded that Article 60(4) and (5) UNCLOS establish the possibility for protective mechanisms? The maximum extent of 500 metres for safety zones historically derives from Article 5(3) of the 1958 Geneva Convention on the Continental Shelf and was originally conceived primarily for the avoidance of collisions between civilian vessels and maritime infrastructures [20]. In the operational reality of sophisticated hybrid threats (such as fast-approaching unmanned underwater vehicles), this 500-metre radius proves insufficient to ensure a timely response. Moreover, the extent of the protective measures a coastal State can take within the safety zone is disputed [21]. It follows that Article 60 UNCLOS was not designed for the hybrid and technologically advanced threats of the 21st century, and its wording may harbour unintended obstacles for addressing these challenges [22].

A unilateral extension of these zones beyond 500 metres would remain difficult to defend dogmatically. Exceptions require authorisation by generally accepted international standards, in practice by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) [23].

The systematic finding nevertheless stands: International law addresses the need to protect maritime infrastructures through the establishment of safety zones, not through the legitimisation of physical defensive perimeters at sea.

Furthermore, Article 60(3), second sentence, UNCLOS prescribes an obligation to remove abandoned or disused installations and structures. For these entities, the provision underscores the purely temporary, purpose-bound nature of their construction and likewise speaks, on systematic grounds against the establishment of permanent military defence fortifications.

E. Interim Conclusion

A systematic interpretation of Article 60 UNCLOS, together with the freedoms of other States in the EEZ (Article 58 UNCLOS), demonstrates that the existing law of the sea does not establish an express competence for the construction of infrastructures in the EEZ for the sole purpose of military protection. The coastal State is subject to far-reaching restrictions that strictly limit the cases in which it may exercise a form of sovereignty and tie the construction of installations to economic purposes. Therefore, significant doctrinal and systematic constraints stand against an expansive interpretation permitting the establishment of large-scale maritime security architectures.

IV. POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

The qualification of hybrid attacks under international law is of central importance for justifying any protective installations. Hybrid sabotage typically manifests in acts such as GPS spoofing, the deployment of unmanned systems, or the severing of cables through alleged anchoring incidents involving civilian vessels [24]. Such acts are often deliberately calibrated so as not to clearly cross the threshold of an ‘armed attack’ within the meaning of Article 51 of the UN Charter [25].

While Article 2(4) of the UN Charter may well be called upon in such grey areas, the issue lies in the fact that the right of military self-defence under Article 51 of the UN Charter is not clearly triggered. State or State-affiliated actors deliberately exploit these problems of attribution, enforcement, and threshold, which is why classical reactive approaches to deterrence frequently fail. It is precisely this lack of effective reactive options that accounts for the high practical relevance of a preventive approach, for instance through the construction of protective structures [26].

Where protective structures cannot be clearly assigned to a competence title derived from Article 56 read in conjunction with Article 60(1) UNCLOS, Article 59 UNCLOS offers a pertinent point of reference as a subsidiary standard for the resolution of unattributed competence conflicts [27]. It is essential that the sovereign rights conferred on the coastal State by Article 56 UNCLOS and the jurisdiction over infrastructures recognised in Article 60 UNCLOS are not deprived of their practical effectiveness. In this regard, the *effet utile* principle supports the view that narrowly circumscribed preventive protective measures may at least be

understood as functionally necessary ancillary measures in guaranteeing the effectiveness of specific rights.

The protection gap against acts falling below the threshold of Article 51 of the UN Charter cannot give rise to a new kind of maritime security architecture, where a network of protective infrastructures were built in EEZs across the globe. It does, however, reinforce the argument that, at a minimum, proportionate preventive protective measures for the safeguarding of the coastal State’s economic rights cannot be denied outright. Against this background, the construction of surveillance platforms for situational awareness and early threat detection appears more defensible as a measure under the law of the sea than the establishment of operational intervention architectures [28].

Article 59 UNCLOS gains particular significance in this regard for the equity-guided understanding of borderline cases in which a measure cannot be clearly considered as a right of the coastal State [29]. The lawfulness of protective measures ultimately depends on whether they remain functionally linked to the protected infrastructures, are limited in their intrusiveness to what is necessary, and give sufficient consideration to the interests of other States. This ancillary competence is, however, strictly limited by the due regard obligation arising from Articles 56(2) and 58(3) UNCLOS. A sea-based surveillance platform for the protection of infrastructure can consequently only be permissible if it does not disproportionately impair international shipping. A far-reaching sovereign closure of extensive EEZ areas under the guise of infrastructure protection, by contrast, appears unlawful [30].

V. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

UNCLOS was negotiated in the 1970s and could anticipate neither the realities of modern hybrid threat scenarios nor today’s geoeconomic dependence on submarine data and energy infrastructures. The authority of coastal States to establish protective structures in the EEZ primarily to counter such threats therefore lies in a legally controversial area. Neither does the textual asymmetry regarding ‘artificial islands’ (Article 60(1)(a)) constitute a *carte blanche* for the militarisation of the EEZ, nor do the principles of freedom of navigation, the due regard obligation, or the 500-metre breadth of safety zones permit an unregulated expansion of national security architecture.

Initiatives such as the NATO operation Baltic Sentry and the NATO Maritime Centre for Security of Critical Undersea Infrastructure (NMCSUI), established under MARCOM, represent important steps towards an operational response [31].

The underlying doctrinal question, however, remains unresolved. Whether and to what extent more far-reaching protective competences may crystallise in the future as customary international law will depend on sufficiently consistent State practice and a corresponding *opinio juris*. Much speaks in favour of recourse to the least intrusive means, such as transparent routing measures, the integration of Vessel Traffic Services (VTS), and the development of binding IMO standards.

In summary, protective structures in the EEZ appear lawful only insofar as they can be justified as functionally necessary ancillary measures for the exercise of the rights under Article 56 UNCLOS. In borderline cases, they

additionally require an equity-guided appreciation pursuant to Article 59 UNCLOS. They should remain anchored in the internal logic of Article 60 UNCLOS (jurisdiction, notification, marking, removal, strictly limited safety zones) and be designed in strict compliance with the principle of proportionality in light of the due regard obligation. Conversely, the construction of a large-scale, maritime ‘security architecture’ without a sufficient basis in international law or international standards, in particular through the IMO, remains unlawful.

REFERENCES

- [1] For an overview of damage to European submarine infrastructure, see Lott, *Conventional Jurisdictional Approaches to Protecting Submarine Cables and Pipelines*, 2025, pp. 63 et seq.
- [2] Cf. Schneider, *Schutz maritimer Kritischer Infrastruktur in der Ostsee*, BAKS 2025, p. 1.
- [3] Sari, *Protecting maritime infrastructure from hybrid threats*, 2025, pp. 6 et seq.
- [4] On the absence of legal definitions in UNCLOS, see Proelss, in: Proelss (ed.), *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea: A Commentary*, 2017, Art. 60, mn. 10.
- [5] See also Kohl, *Dickinson Law Review*, 2018, p. 930 et seq.
- [6] On the distinction under the law of the sea between installations and on the classification of military and acoustic surveillance systems, see Treves, *AJIL* 1980, pp. 840 et seq.
- [7] Article 60(1)(b) UNCLOS.
- [8] Cf. also Sun, *Finding a Balance in the Exclusive Economic Zone*, 2025, pp. 255 et seq.
- [9] On the reality of state practice deviating from these regulatory limits, see Proelss, in: Proelss (ed.), *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea: A Commentary*, 2017, Art. 60, mn. 13.
- [10] Sun, *Finding a Balance in the Exclusive Economic Zone*, 2025, pp. 45 et seq. Sun describes the development of the EEZ as a response to expanded coastal State claims that were, at the same time, not intended to interrupt the freedom interests of other States.
- [11] See Sun, *Finding a Balance in the Exclusive Economic Zone*, pp. 201 et seq.; it is expressly noted there that military activities in the EEZ belong to the rights not expressly attributed, that States are in disagreement on this point, and that Part V UNCLOS does not expressly regulate security interests. Additionally Oude Elferink, *Artificial Islands, Installations, and Structures*, in: Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law, mn. 15, on the explanation of the restrictions on ‘installations and structures’ arising from the interests of maritime States in military devices in foreign EEZs.
- [12] UNCLOS, Articles 56(2), 58(3), 59 and 60(3), (5), (7) and (8). These provisions demonstrate that the construction competence operates within a balanced EEZ regime and is constrained by due regard obligations, safety zone rules, sea lane provisions, and status limitations; see also the systematic reading in Oude Elferink, *Artificial Islands, Installations, and Structures*, mn. 16.
- [13] See Nandan/Rosenne (eds.), *Virginia Commentary*, Vol. II, Art. 60, paras. 60.15(b)–(i).
- [14] Coastal States do not exercise full sovereignty but merely functional competences. See Beckman/Davenport, *The EEZ Regime: Reflections after 30 Years*, 2012, pp. 6 et seq.
- [15] The term describes historical and ongoing efforts to extend national legal orders onto EEZ and the high seas. See Molenaar, *New Maritime Zones and the Law of the Sea*, in: Henrik Ringbom (ed.), 2015, pp. 249 et seq.
- [16] On the systematic nexus between coastal State rights and navigational freedoms in the EEZ, see Sun, *Finding a Balance in the Exclusive Economic Zone*, 2025, pp. 77 et seq.
- [17] See generally Beckman/Davenport, *The EEZ Regime*, 2012, pp. 16 et seq.
- [18] On the controversy regarding military activities in the EEZ and on the interpretation of the reservation of peaceful purposes, see Sun, *Finding a Balance in the Exclusive Economic Zone*, 2025, pp. 212 et seq.
- [19] This systematic reading is supported by the fact that UNCLOS explicitly ties the extension of safety zones to the standards of the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and rejects unilateral spatial claims.
- [20] Cf. Nordquist et al., *The Virginia Commentary*, Vol. II, 1993, pp. 584 et seq. (on Article 60(4) and (5)); on the historical adoption of the 500-metre zone from the 1958 Continental Shelf Convention for the purpose of civilian collision avoidance.
- [21] On the operational vulnerability of offshore installations at close range, see Center for International Maritime Security (CIMSEC), *Offshore Installations: Practical Security and Legal Considerations*, 2013. On the issue of competences in the safety zone, see Proelss, in: Proelss (ed.), *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea: A Commentary*, 2017, Art. 60, mn. 25.
- [22] Ringbom, *New Threats-Old Rules: Law of the Sea Issues Raised by Suspected Attacks on Submarine Infrastructure in the Baltic Sea*, 56 *Ocean Development & International Law*, 2025, p. 408. Additionally see generally Sari, *Protecting maritime infrastructure from hybrid threats*, 2025, on the gaps in UNCLOS in addressing modern hybrid attacks; additionally CIMSEC, *Offshore Installations*, 2013.
- [23] IMO, Document LEG/MISC.8, pp. 38 et seq. Exceptions beyond 500 metres generally require proceedings before the IMO.
- [24] Proelß/Wollensak, *Rechtsgutachten zur Schattenflotte*, 2026, pp. 3 et seq.
- [25] See Fogt, *Legal Challenges or "Gaps" by Countering Hybrid Warfare - Building Resilience in Jus Ante Bellum*, 27 *Sw. J. Int'l L.*, 2020, pp. 66, 68-69 noting that hybrid threats are designed to stay under the triggering threshold for an armed attack.
- [26] Generally see Zombory, *Legal Aspects of Hybrid Threats and Warfare*, in: Katarzyna Zombory and János Ede Szilágyi (eds.), *Shielding Europe with the Common Security and Defence Policy: The EU Legal Framework for the Development of an Innovative European Defence Industry in Times of a Changing Global Security Environment*, 2024, pp. 769 et seq.; on the legal vacuum in criminal prosecution, see Hartmann/Lott, *The Prosecution ‘Gap’ for Attacks on Subsea Cables and Pipelines*, EJIL: Talk!, 2025.
- [27] See Proelss, in: Proelss (ed.), *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea: A Commentary*, 2017, Art. 60, mn. 13. Additionally Oude Elferink, *Artificial Islands, Installations, and Structures*, in: Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law, mn. 15.
- [28] On the essential distinction under the law of the sea between permissible reconnaissance measures (situational awareness) and more intrusive operational defence measures, see Sari, *Protecting maritime infrastructure from hybrid threats*, 2025, pp. 23 et seq.
- [29] On the invocation of Article 59 UNCLOS as a central equity and conflict-resolution norm for the possibility of protective installations in the EEZ, see Sun, *Finding a Balance in the Exclusive Economic Zone*, pp. 252 et seq. Additionally Oude Elferink, *Artificial Islands, Installations, and Structures*, in: Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law, para. 16. For critical considerations regarding the justification of military activities under Article 59, see Beckman/Davenport, *The EEZ Regime*, 2012, p. 26.
- [30] On the obligation of mutual due regard in the event of competing interests in the EEZ, see fundamentally Sun, *Finding a Balance in the Exclusive Economic Zone*, 2025, pp. 130 et seq.
- [31] Allied Maritime Command, *NATO officially launches new Maritime Centre for Security of Critical Undersea Infrastructure*, Press Release, 2024, available at: <https://mc.nato.int/media-centre/news/2024/nato-officially-launches-new-nmcscui>